

Structuration in the water/ethanol/ethyl acetate ternary system.

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Abstract

In the frame of extraction of biologically relevant compounds by liquid-liquid phase separation, the performances and structure of the ternary ethyl acetate / water / ethanol are compared to those of the historical chloroform / water / methanol system proposed by Folch. The organic and aqueous phases in equilibrium with and without added compounds are measured by SAXS in the high q range (nm scale).

The main observation is the difference in behaviour as UFME for both systems, for the blank samples, and when adding compounds.

The Folch system shows the presence of clusters only in the CHCl_3 -rich phase, not in the water-rich phase, with or without additives. I have found previously that the water-rich phase does exhibit clusters but only near the critical point.

The new ternary shows the presence of clusters in both the organic and aqueous phases without compounds; clusters in the aqueous phase might improve the solubilisation of phospholipids, which is not desirable.

In addition, clusters in the organic phase are vanishing when adding compounds to extract, while in the aqueous phase the situation is more complicated, with low q intensity increasing or decreasing depending on the sample.

Finally, in many cases, even blank samples (no added compound) with the new mixtures have different spectra while supposedly situated on the same tie-line. Therefore there is an issue regarding sample preparation or sample preservation.

1 Materials & Methods

1.1 Samples

Samples were received prepared and frozen, and were kept in a freezer at -20°C until 2 days before the measurement. For 48 h, they were placed in a cold room 6°C . For approximately 4 h before the experiment, they were placed at room temperature ($23.5(5)^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 1: Phase diagram of the ternary system chloroform / water / methanol with compositions of the samples before phase separation. 3 composition, 2 phases, preparations with and without additives, amounting to 12 samples.

The reference system is from Folch (fig. 1). 3 samples are prepared along one tie-line. We expect to always find the same phases, only in different ratios.

The new system proposed as a replacement for Folch has a different phase diagram with more solubility between water and the oil (fig. 2). 9 samples are prepared along 3 tie-lines. For each tie-line we expect to always find the same phases, only in different ratios.

1.2 SAXS on ID02@ESRF

Small Angle X-rays Scattering data were acquired with a beam monochromatised at 12 459 eV corresponding to a wavelength of 0.0995 nm, selected with the 111 plan of a silicon crystal (relative energy bandwidth: 2×10^{-4}). A 2 mm graphite filter was used to produce a large Gaussian beam, spreading the flux over a large cross-section to reduce the risk of radiation damages. A horizontally reflecting toroidal mirror was used; collimation and beam cleaning were achieved via the adjustments of the two primary and 5 secondary slits. The beam at the sample was estimated to be 0.4 mm \times 0.8 mm (v \times h).

AC = Avec composés
 SC = Sans composé => additifs seuls

Echantillon avec composés. Nomenclature dans la boîte

AC	Ech	Phase orga	Phase aqueuse
	1	2 org	3 aq
	2	4 org	4 aq
	3	7 org	7 aq
	4	10 org	10 aq
	5	13 org	13 aq
	6	16 org	16 aq
	7	19 org	20 aq
	8	22 org	22 aq
	9	25 org	25 aq
	10	28 org	28 aq
	11	31 org	31 aq
	12	34 org	34 aq

SC	Ech	ϕ_{org}	ϕ_{aq}
	1	1 org	1 aq
	2	2 org	2 aq
	3	3 org	3 aq
	4	4 org	4 aq
	5	5 org	5 aq
	6	6 org	6 aq
	7	7 org	7 aq
	8	8 org	8 aq
	9	9 org	9 aq
	10	10 org	10 aq
	11	11 org	11 aq
	12	12 org	12 aq

ETAC = Ethyl Acetate
 ETOH = Ethanol
 Eau

$CHCl_3$ = Chloroforme
 MeOH = Methanol

Figure 2: Phase diagram of the ternary system ethyl acetate / water / ethanol with compositions of the samples before phase separation. 9 compositions, 2 phases, preparations with and without additives, amounting to **36 samples** measured by S. Prévost.

The sample-to-detector distance was 0.78 cm as measured with the Bragg peaks of silver behenate placed at the sample position.

Samples were injected in a quartz (10 μm wall thickness) flow-through capillary of diameter 2.375(25) mm as determined by transmission scan. The capillary was not thermalised, but the experimental hutch is kept at 23.0(5) $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Scattering intensities were recorded on a Rayonix MX-170HS CCD detector of 17 cm side and 3840×3840 pixels operated in low-noise mode and 8×8 binning.

Ten acquisitions of 1 s were recorded to evaluate the standard-deviation, always at the same position in the capillary to avoid changes in surface scattering.

Data reduction was performed using the standard tool-chain at ID02, using the transmitted photon flux measured by a PIN diode on the beam stop, and a normalization factor to account for the ratio of efficiency of this PIN diode and the detector. The scattering from the empty capillary was subtracted. The normalization factor was adjusted by the level of water, assumed to be at $1.68 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ from the tabulated (NIST) isothermal compressibility and density of water.

For samples containing chloroform, the transmission was in the range $2 \times 10^{-4} - 3.5 \times 10^{-4}$, which is extremely low, with two consequences: (i) the absolute scale is doubtful, and (ii) all instrumental artifacts, normally negligible, may become dominant: air and windows scattering, presence of harmonics (photons of higher energies, which will produce scattering at a wrong q value) etc.

2 SAXS data and fits

2.1 Model and parameters

The SAXS data cover a q -range from ca. 0.15 nm^{-1} to 10 nm^{-1} , corresponding in direct space to distances of about 0.6 nm to 40 nm, with the rough assumption that $q \approx \frac{2\pi}{d}$.

The high q already correspond to the range where molecular scattering takes place, as seen in the data by an upturn of intensity. Scattering by molecules in a liquid can be fitted by a sum of Lorentzian functions. This requires however to measure scattering in the range where peaks are visible, which is not the case here. Therefore, a Lorentzian is used to reproduce the upturn at high q .

$$I_L(q) = \frac{\frac{I_L \cdot \xi_L}{\pi}}{1 + (\xi_L \cdot (q - q_L))^2}$$

The corresponding parameters are only *ad hoc*, because there is no peak in the experimental q -range; this Lorentzian only serves the purpose of repro-

ducing the intensity upturn in the WAXS range and a non-flat background in the SAXS range.

For non fluorescent atoms at the energy of 12.46 keV used here (all imaginary parts of scattering lengths of C, H, N, O, Cl are indeed negligible) and with a coherence volume much larger than the scattering volume, we do not expect any flat (isotropic) background. Indeed, with WAXS data available and fitted with a sum of Lorentzians, I found previously that there was no need for an additional constant background. As again we do not have WAXS data here, the single Lorentzian function is not sufficient and a constant background is added.

Finally, the density fluctuations corresponding to the existence of an UFME are as usual fitted with an Ornstein-Zernicke equation, which is a Lorentzian with its peak at $q = 0$.

$$I_{OZ}(q) = \frac{I_{OZ}(0)}{1 + (\xi_{OZ} \cdot q)^2}$$

It only needs 2 parameters, the intensity and the characteristic dimension. However, both parameters and in particular ξ_{OZ} are very sensitive to the background, here fitted by a constant and a Lorentzian. The uncertainty on the determination of ξ_{OZ} is hard to estimate. I did make a number of fits, including fits over sectors of the 2D patterns (2D data split into 16 data sets, corresponding to azimuthal sectors of 22.5°) but I still need to validate the results to make some uncertainty estimate.

Note that, contrary to the case with octan-1-ol, we do not see any peak in the q -range where Ornstein-Zernicke fluctuations scatter. We only see an actual peak for pure ethanol, in the high q part of the spectrum.

The data are therefore fitted with the following model:

$$I_{UFME}(q) = \frac{I_{OZ}(0)}{1 + (\xi_{OZ} \cdot q)^2} + \frac{\frac{I_L \cdot \xi_L}{\pi}}{1 + (\xi_L \cdot (q - q_L))^2} + I_{\text{bkg}} \quad (1)$$

The most reliable parameters seem to be the Ornstein-Zernicke forward scattering $I_{OZ}(0)$ and the total forward scattering $I_{UFME}(0) = I_{OZ}(0) + \frac{(I_L \cdot \xi_L)/\pi}{1 + (\xi_L \cdot q_L)^2} + I_{\text{bkg}}$.

2.2 SAXS data

2.2.1 Pure solvents

Of the 4 pure solvents, whose data are plotted fig. 3, only water and ethyl acetate present without a doubt a minimum (at respectively $q \approx 4 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and $q \approx 1.2 \text{ nm}^{-1}$), as a sign for the presence of nm-sized density fluctuations. It may also be the case for chloroform, though comparison between sector-averaged data rather indicate an artifact; measurements should be done in

a different way with far less absorption of the beam to be sure. For MeOH and EtOH, there is no visible OZ contribution (no minimum of intensity between high and low q), though by fits a contribution is found in both cases. Whether this OZ part is real or due to the model being not physically good enough is unknown.

Figure 3: SAXS spectra from the pure solvents, with expected intensity from electron density and compressibility (dotted lines), and fits with eq. (1). For CHCl_3 , keep in mind the adverse conditions for measurements; the increase of intensity at low q is certainly not real, and the absolute scale is likely underestimated by 30 %.

Solvent	$I_{\text{UFME}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$I_{\text{OZ}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$\xi_{\text{OZ}} / \text{nm}$
Water	1.73×10^{-3}	5.0×10^{-4}	0.23
MeOH	2.77×10^{-3}	6.7×10^{-4}	0.46
EtOH	2.62×10^{-3}	8.0×10^{-4}	0.36
EtOAc	3.36×10^{-3}	6.5×10^{-4}	0.54
CHCl ₃	4.93×10^{-3}	4.37×10^{-3}	0.22

Table 1: Fit results for pure solvents fig. 3 with eq. (1).

Solvent	$I_{\text{UFME}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$I_{\text{OZ}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$\xi_{\text{OZ}} / \text{nm}$
Water	1.73×10^{-3}	0.50×10^{-3}	0.23
MeOH	2.77×10^{-3}	0.67×10^{-3}	0.46
CHCl_3	4.93×10^{-3}	4.37×10^{-3}	0.22
SC10aq	2.23×10^{-3}	0.12×10^{-3}	0.53
SC11aq	2.61×10^{-3}	0.22×10^{-3}	0.53
SC12aq	2.67×10^{-3}	0.23×10^{-3}	0.47
SC10orga	8.91×10^{-3}	8.16×10^{-3}	0.33
SC11orga	9.41×10^{-3}	7.88×10^{-3}	0.33
SC12orga	8.21×10^{-3}	7.59×10^{-3}	0.30
AC28aq	2.23×10^{-3}	0.12×10^{-3}	0.55
AC31aq	2.59×10^{-3}	0.20×10^{-3}	0.48
AC34aq	2.66×10^{-3}	0.24×10^{-3}	0.45
AC28orga	9.67×10^{-3}	7.94×10^{-3}	0.36
AC31orga	9.99×10^{-3}	8.23×10^{-3}	0.36
AC34orga	8.93×10^{-3}	8.31×10^{-3}	0.29

Table 2: Fit results for the Folch system (see diagram fig. 1 and SAXS spectra fig. 4).

2.2.2 Folch system

From the scattering of phases in the Folch reference system (figs. 4 to 6), we find that only the CHCl_3 -rich phases exhibit clear OZ-like fluctuations. This is highlighted by subtracting the scattering from pure CHCl_3 leading to data on fig. 5. This is possible because the organic phase is essentially made of CHCl_3 . For the 3 positions along the tie-line, and with or without compound, the intensities are the same in the organic phase; the same is true for the aqueous phases. For some reason, the intensities are lower for SC10aq and for AC28aq than for the other aqueous phases, but the trend is the same. Note that there is a doubt whether AC28aq was measured, or if SC10aq was measured twice instead.

Figure 4: SAXS spectra for the reference system from Folch: $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MeOH}/\text{CHCl}_3$. Left side: aqueous phases, right side: organic phases. Top: blanks, without additives. Bottom: phases with additives. For CHCl_3 -rich solutions, keep in mind the adverse conditions for measurements; the increase of intensity at low q is certainly not real, and the absolute scale is likely underestimated by 30 %.

Figure 5: SAXS spectra for the CHCl_3 -rich samples, where the scattering by pure CHCl_3 has been subtracted, to demonstrate the presence of Ornstein-Zernicke-like fluctuations.

Figure 6: SAXS spectra for the H₂O-rich samples, highlighting the disappearance of OZ fluctuations in the water-rich phases, with or without additives. Note that there is a doubt whether AC28aq was measured, or if SC10aq was measured twice instead.

Solvent	$I_{\text{UFME}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$I_{\text{OZ}}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$\xi_{\text{OZ}} / \text{nm}$
Water	1.73×10^{-3}	0.50×10^{-3}	0.23
EtOH	2.62×10^{-3}	0.80×10^{-3}	0.36
EtOAc	3.36×10^{-3}	0.65×10^{-3}	0.54
SC01aq	3.58×10^{-3}	2.09×10^{-3}	0.65
SC02aq	2.07×10^{-3}	0.67×10^{-3}	0.39
SC03aq	7.03×10^{-3}	5.43×10^{-3}	0.98
SC01orga	5.32×10^{-3}	2.78×10^{-3}	0.75
SC02orga	3.84×10^{-3}	1.29×10^{-3}	0.51
SC03orga	10.55×10^{-3}	8.03×10^{-3}	1.23
AC03aq	31.1×10^{-3}	29.2×10^{-3}	2.18
AC04aq	2.33×10^{-3}	0.79×10^{-3}	0.38
AC07aq	2.66×10^{-3}	0.89×10^{-3}	0.39
AC02orga	3.31×10^{-3}	0.45×10^{-3}	0.37
AC04orga	3.35×10^{-3}	0.55×10^{-3}	0.41
AC07orga	3.32×10^{-3}	0.53×10^{-3}	0.44

Table 3: Fit results for the ethyl acetate / ethanol / water system (see diagram fig. 2 and SAXS spectra fig. 7).

2.2.3 System with ethyl acetate

As a marked difference to Folch, SAXS data for the ternary with ethyl acetate, ethanol and water (figs. 7 to 9) show strong OZ behaviour for all organic and aqueous phases without compounds.

Adding compounds lead to no visible OZ behaviour for all organic phases, for all 9 samples.

Adding compounds also lead to changes in the low q behaviour for all aqueous phases, but with no clear trend. In some cases the intensity increases, in some cases it decreases.

Rather worryingly, for each tie-line, the spectra, with or without additives, are different, i.e. we are not looking at actual identical liquids, as would be expected for samples on a tie-line.

Figure 7: Solutions from the top line (samples 1, 2 and 3) in fig. 2. Left side: aqueous phases, right side: organic phases. Top: blanks, without additives. Bottom: phases with additives.

Figure 8: Solutions from the middle line (samples 4, 5 and 6) in fig. 2. Left side: aqueous phases, right side: organic phases. Top: blanks, without additives. Bottom: phases with additives.

Solvent	$I_{UFME}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$I_{OZ}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	ξ_{OZ} / nm
Water	1.73×10^{-3}	0.50×10^{-3}	0.23
EtOH	2.62×10^{-3}	0.80×10^{-3}	0.36
EtOAc	3.36×10^{-3}	0.65×10^{-3}	0.54
SC04aq	4.45×10^{-3}	2.92×10^{-3}	0.76
SC05aq	5.30×10^{-3}	3.75×10^{-3}	0.83
SC06aq	4.42×10^{-3}	2.90×10^{-3}	0.75
SC04orga	6.49×10^{-3}	3.95×10^{-3}	0.89
SC05orga	7.77×10^{-3}	5.24×10^{-3}	1.01
SC06orga	5.71×10^{-3}	3.18×10^{-3}	0.79
AC10aq	2.16×10^{-3}	0.73×10^{-3}	0.37
AC13aq	2.17×10^{-3}	0.76×10^{-3}	0.38
AC16aq	2.93×10^{-3}	1.42×10^{-3}	0.51
AC10orga	3.29×10^{-3}	0.51×10^{-3}	0.42
AC13orga	3.31×10^{-3}	0.56×10^{-3}	0.43
AC16orga	3.37×10^{-3}	0.63×10^{-3}	0.43

Table 4: Fit results for the ethyl acetate / ethanol / water system (see diagram fig. 2 and SAXS spectra fig. 8).

Solvent	$I_{UFME}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	$I_{OZ}(0) / \text{mm}^{-1}$	ξ_{OZ} / nm
Water	1.73×10^{-3}	0.50×10^{-3}	0.23
EtOH	2.62×10^{-3}	0.80×10^{-3}	0.36
EtOAc	3.36×10^{-3}	0.65×10^{-3}	0.54
SC07aq	6.67×10^{-3}	5.08×10^{-3}	0.96
SC08aq	7.39×10^{-3}	5.79×10^{-3}	1.03
SC09aq	4.55×10^{-3}	3.02×10^{-3}	0.82
SC07orga	8.91×10^{-3}	6.38×10^{-3}	1.10
SC08orga	9.05×10^{-3}	6.53×10^{-3}	1.11
SC09orga	5.75×10^{-3}	3.23×10^{-3}	0.76
AC20aq	25.2×10^{-3}	23.4×10^{-3}	1.98
AC22aq	9.42×10^{-3}	7.58×10^{-3}	1.16
AC25aq	4.10×10^{-3}	2.56×10^{-3}	0.69
AC19orga	3.35×10^{-3}	0.58×10^{-3}	0.43
AC22orga	3.38×10^{-3}	0.63×10^{-3}	0.44
AC25orga	3.56×10^{-3}	0.91×10^{-3}	0.45

Table 5: Fit results for the ethyl acetate / ethanol / water system (see diagram fig. 2 and SAXS spectra fig. 9).

Figure 9: Solutions from the bottom line (samples 7, 8 and 9) in fig. 2. Left side: aqueous phases, right side: organic phases. Top: blanks, without additives. Bottom: phases with additives.